

HUNERMAND ANDROID APP

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DECLARATION

Except where otherwise acknowledge in the text, this thesis represent the original project of the authors. The materials here have not been submitted either whole or in part, for a degree at this or any other university/ institute/ DAI (Degree Awarding Institute).

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APPROVAL CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the research work presented in this thesis, entitled, **Hunermand Android App**, is conducted by Bilal Ahmed and Wajid Ali under the supervision of Mr. Azhid Ali. No part of this thesis has been submitted anywhere else for any other degree. This thesis is submitted to the Department of Computer Science/BS Computer Science Government College Daggar, University of Buner in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Studies in Computer Science (BSCS).

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DEDICATION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.Introduction

In the current days, digital platforms have changed how services are provided from freelancing platforms like Fiverr and Upwork to work from home, these platforms proved their services to connect professionals with buyers. However these platforms fail to address the specific needs of local service providers, such as plumbers, electricians, and carpenters, and Customers looking for their services in their communities. These local job markets require platforms that are tailored to their unique needs, such as location-based search, direct communication, and the ability to verify skills and experience.

“HUNERMAND” means “Experts” in Urdu, aim to fill this gap by offering digital local job solution that connect skilled people with interested clients. This app provide two directional offertunities, allowing experts to display their skills and services while interested clients to post or find professional experts according to their specific needs.It not only facilitates communication but also builds trust by enabling users to create comprehensive profiles that include work experience, certifications, and contact information.

1.1 Used Software:

1.1.1 Kotlin: The app is developed using Kotlin, a modern programming language well-suited and highly google recommended for Android applications.

1.1.2 Firebase Database: backend is powered by Firebase Real-time Database, a NoSQL cloud database that guarantees real-time data synchronization, ensuring the platform remains responsive and current.

1.1.3 Adobe Illustrator: Moreover, Adobe Illustrator is used to design logo for the app.

Hunerman makes use of modern mobile technologies to provide:

Instant Communication: Immediate updates for job postings, profile modifications, and direct contact between buyers and experts.

User-Friendly Design: An interface that allows buyers and experts to communicate seamlessly.

Scalability: A backend system capable of accommodating an increasing number of users and data.

By prioritizing the needs of local job markets, Hunermand guarantees that locating and hiring experts is streamlined, transparent, and tailored to the users' needs.

1.2 Objectives:

The objectives of **Hunermand android app** are aligned with its goal to streamline local job markets and provide an efficient connection between Experts and clients. These objectives include:

1.2.1 Connection between Experts and Buyers:

To create a platform where experts and buyers can easily find each other based on skills, location, and job requirements.

1.2.2 Profile Management:

Allowing users to create and edit profiles, including work experience, certifications, and contact details.

Ensuring that profiles are accessible in real-time to buyers and experts.

1.2.3 Facilitating Real-Time Interaction:

Using **Firestore Real-time Database** to ensure job postings, profile updates, and communication occur in real time without delays.

1.2.4 Promoting Trust and Transparency:

Introducing features like certifications, and detailed job descriptions to enhance credibility.

1.3 Unique Features of Hunermand:

1.3.1 Two Types of User:

The app distinguishes between **experts (hunermand)** and **buyers (zaroratmand)**:

Experts: Can list their skills, certifications, and availability, and search for posted jobs and can post a job if needed

Buyers: Can post job requirements, search for experts, and contact them directly.

1.3.2 Search Functionality:

Advanced filters allow users to search by skillset, job category, or availability.

The app's search results are powered by **Firestore Queries**, ensuring accuracy and real-time updates.

1.3.3 Direct Communication:

By providing contact information (Phone number, WhatsApp number) enable direct contact between buyers and experts, fostering trust and improving negotiation efficiency.

1.3.4 Real-Time Job Listings:

Jobs posted by buyers are immediately visible to relevant experts, thanks to Firestore's real-time synchronization capabilities.

1.4 Benefits of Hunermand:

1.4.1 For Experts:

Increased visibility for their services within local communities.

A platform to showcase skills, certifications, and customer reviews.

Real-time job opportunities tailored to their expertise and location.

1.4.2 For Buyers:

Find perfect experts for their basic need in their area.

The ability to post job requirements and receive responses instantly.

Enhanced trust through detailed profiles and certifications.

1.4.3 For Both:

Direct communication without intermediaries.

Time-saving features like real-time updates and intuitive search filters.

A secure environment backed by Firebase Authentication.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2. Literature Review

2.1 Evolution of Service Platforms

In today's digital world, many platforms have emerged to connect service providers with potential clients. These platforms have revolutionized how services are offered and consumed, creating opportunities for freelancers and professionals to showcase their skills and connect with buyers. Among the most popular platforms are TaskRabbit, Fiverr, and Upwork, each of which offers unique functionalities. However, these platforms primarily cater to a global or generalized audience, leaving gaps in addressing the specific needs of localized job markets, especially for specialized trades like plumbing, carpentry, or electrical work.

2.2 Limitations of Existing Platforms

TaskRabbit:

TaskRabbit focuses on local job markets and aims to connect people with skilled professionals for tasks such as furniture assembly, home repairs, or moving services. While TaskRabbit is one of the few platforms to address localized services, its availability is restricted to specific cities and regions, and the range of service categories is limited. Additionally, TaskRabbit operates with an hourly pricing model, which may not suit all types of jobs or client preferences.

Fiverr and Upwork:

Fiverr and Upwork are leading freelancing platforms that offer a wide range of services, from graphic design and content writing to IT support and digital marketing. These platforms excel in connecting freelancers with clients globally but often fall short in addressing local job markets. For instance, a buyer looking for a plumber or electrician in their neighborhood may not find relevant listings on these platforms. Moreover, Fiverr and Upwork are predominantly focused on remote, project-based work, which limits their effectiveness for on-site service requirements.

2.3 Challenges in Localized Job Markets

The lack of a dedicated platform for local tradespeople creates significant challenges for both service providers and buyers. Professionals in specialized trades often struggle to market their skills and reach potential clients, while buyers face difficulties finding trustworthy experts within their geographical region. Traditional methods, such as relying on word-of-mouth recommendations or classified ads, are not only outdated but also inefficient in today's fast-paced digital world.

2.4 Hunermand: A Tailored Solution

In contrast, **Hunermand** stands out by specifically targeting local job markets and specialized trades. The app is designed to connect professionals directly with buyers in their vicinity, focusing on practical job categories such as plumbing, electrical work, carpentry, and more. This localized approach ensures that both experts and buyers benefit from a streamlined, efficient platform tailored to their needs.

2.5 Leveraging Modern Technology

What sets Hunermand apart is its use of modern technology to overcome the limitations of traditional job boards and existing platforms. By leveraging Firebase Realtime Database, the app ensures that all data—whether it's a job posting, profile update, or message—is synchronized across all connected devices in real time. This feature eliminates delays, providing users with an up-to-date and seamless experience. Unlike other platforms, which may require manual refreshes or updates, Hunermand automates these processes, ensuring that users always have the latest information at their fingertips.

2.6 Enhancing Usability and Transparency

Hunermand prioritizes ease of use and accessibility for both buyers and experts. Buyers can post detailed job descriptions, search for professionals based on specific skills and locations, and contact experts directly through the app. Experts, on the other hand, can create comprehensive profiles showcasing their skills, certifications, and experience. This two-way functionality enhances trust and transparency, making it easier for users to connect and collaborate.

2.7 Bridging the Gap in Local Job Markets

By focusing on localized services and leveraging advanced technologies, **Hunermann** addresses the shortcomings of existing platforms while providing a tailored solution for local job markets. It bridges the gap between professionals and clients, ensuring that hiring and being hired is a simple, efficient, and trustworthy process.

Chapter 3

Proposed System

3. Proposed System

The proposed system for **Hunermant** aims to address the challenges faced by local job experts and buyers in finding and connecting with each other. Unlike traditional methods such as classified ads or word-of-mouth referrals, this system leverages modern technologies to provide an efficient, transparent, and user-friendly platform. The proposed system is designed to simplify the process of hiring experts and finding jobs through features like real-time updates, detailed profiles, and direct communication.

3.1 System Overview

The **Hunermant** app is a mobile-based platform that connects local job experts, such as plumbers, electricians, and carpenters, with buyers looking for their services. The app facilitates this interaction by providing tools for profile management, job postings, and advanced search functionalities. By utilizing Firebase Real-time Database, the system ensures that all updates are synchronized in real time, creating a seamless user experience.

The system supports two distinct user types:

3.1.1 Experts:

Professionals who offer services in specific fields and want to connect with buyers to gain job opportunities.

3.1.2 Buyers:

Individuals or businesses looking to hire experts for specific tasks or projects.

3.2 System Features

The proposed system includes the following features to meet user needs:

3.2.1 User Registration and Authentication:

Users (both experts and buyers) can register using CNIC.

Firebase Authentication ensures secure login and user data protection.

3.2.2 Profile Management:

Experts can create detailed profiles, listing their skills, certifications, experience, and availability.

Buyers can create profiles specifying their requirements and preferences for hiring experts.

3.2.3 Job Posting and Search:

Buyers can post detailed job descriptions, including category, location, and required skills.

Experts can browse job postings using advanced filters, such as location, job type, or skill requirements.

3.2.4 Direct Communication:

Buyers and experts can communicate directly through contact no. Hunermand app provide the contact direct to phone number, WhatsApp number or through message.

3.2.5 Real-Time Updates:

Changes to profiles, job postings, or messages are reflected instantly across all devices using Firebase Real-time Database.

3.2.5 Scalable Backend:

The system is designed to accommodate a growing user base and additional features, such as payment integration or a rating system, in the future.

3.3 System Workflow

The workflow of the proposed system is designed to ensure a seamless interaction between buyers and experts. The key steps in the workflow are:

3.3.1 User Registration:

Users register and log in to the app using their credentials. Firebase Authentication verifies and secures user accounts.

3.3.2 Profile Creation:

After registration, users complete their profiles. Experts input details about their skills, certifications, and availability, while buyers specify their hiring preferences.

3.3.3 Job Posting:

Buyers post jobs by filling out a form with details such as job type, location, and description. The data is stored in Firebase and becomes visible to relevant experts in real time.

3.3.4 Job Search:

Experts browse job postings using filters and apply for jobs that match their skills and preferences.

3.3.5 Communication:

Once a buyer selects an expert, they can communicate directly through phone number and WhatsApp number

3.4 Advantages of the Proposed System

The proposed system offers several advantages over traditional methods and existing platforms:

3.4.1 Efficiency: The app eliminates the time-consuming process of finding and contacting professionals through traditional methods.

Real-time updates and communication ensure quick responses.

3.4.2 Transparency:

Detailed profiles and job descriptions provide clarity, fostering trust between buyers and experts.

3.4.3 Accessibility:

The app is easy to use and accessible to users with varying levels of technical expertise.

The integration of filters and search tools simplifies navigation.

3.4.4 Scalability:

The backend, powered by Firebase, is designed to handle a growing user base and additional features without performance issues.

3.4.5 Flexibility:

The system supports future enhancements, such as integrating payment gateways or a rating system, ensuring it can adapt to evolving user needs.

3.5 Implementation Plan

The implementation of the proposed system follows a structured approach to ensure efficiency and effectiveness:

3.5.1 Phase 1: Design and Prototyping

Create wireframes and prototypes to visualize the app's interface and user experience.

Use Adobe Illustrator to design UI elements, including logos and icons.

3.5.2 Phase 2: Development

Develop the front-end using Kotlin and integrate it with the backend (Firebase).

Implement core features such as user registration, profile management, job posting, and messaging.

3.5.3 Phase 3: Testing

Test the app for functionality, performance, and security.

3.5.4 Phase 4: Maintenance and Updates

Monitor the app's performance and resolve any bugs or issues.

Introduce new features, such as a rating system or payment integration, based on user feedback.

3.6 Conclusion

The proposed system for **Hunermand** is designed to address the specific challenges of connecting local job experts with buyers. By leveraging modern technologies like Firebase Real-time Database and Kotlin, the system ensures efficiency, transparency, and scalability. Its user-centric design and focus on real-time updates make it a reliable and accessible platform for users. The implementation plan ensures that the system can be developed, tested, and maintained effectively, providing a strong foundation for future growth and enhancements.

Chapter 4

Feasibility Report

4. Feasibility Report

Before the development of the **Hunermann** app, a feasibility study was conducted to ensure that the project was both viable and capable of achieving its objectives. This chapter outlines the technical, operational, economic, and social feasibility of the app, highlighting the factors that contributed to its successful implementation.

4.1 Technical Feasibility

Technical feasibility focuses on whether the technology, tools, and skills required to develop the project are available and sufficient to meet its goals. For the **Hunermann** app, technical feasibility was evaluated based on the following factors:

4.1.1 Technology Stack:

The app was developed using Kotlin, a modern and robust programming language, which offers excellent compatibility with Android Studio and is widely adopted for Android app development.

Firestore Realtime Database was chosen for backend services due to its real-time synchronization, scalability, and seamless integration with mobile platforms.

4.1.2 Development Tools:

The availability of Android Studio, a comprehensive IDE for Android app development, ensured that the team could build and test the app efficiently.

Adobe Illustrator provided the necessary tools to create professional UI/UX designs for the app.

4.1.3 Team Expertise:

The development team possessed the required technical expertise in Android development, Kotlin programming, and Firestore integration.

Tutorials, documentation, and online resources further supplemented knowledge gaps, making technical implementation feasible.

4.2 Operational Feasibility

Operational feasibility assesses how well the proposed solution meets the user's needs and whether it can be effectively integrated into daily use. For **Hunermand**, the following factors were evaluated:

4.2.1 User Needs:

The app directly addresses the need for a platform where local job experts and buyers can connect.

Features such as profile creation, job posting, and real-time communication were designed with user convenience in mind.

4.2.2 Ease of Use:

The app's intuitive interface ensures that both experts and buyers, even those with limited technical knowledge, can navigate it effortlessly.

A clean and minimalistic design was implemented to reduce complexity and enhance user experience.

4.2.3 Maintenance and Support:

Firebase simplifies backend maintenance with automatic updates and real-time synchronization.

The app's modular design ensures that future updates and feature additions can be implemented without disrupting existing functionalities.

4.3 Economic Feasibility

Economic feasibility examines whether the project is financially viable and whether the benefits outweigh the costs. For **Hunermand**, this was analyzed in terms of development, deployment, and potential returns.

4.3.1 Development Costs:

The use of free and open-source tools such as Android Studio and Firebase significantly reduced development costs.

Firebase's pay-as-you-go model ensures that costs remain low during the initial stages of the app, scaling only as user demand grows.

4.3.2 Deployment Costs:

The cost of deploying the app on the Google Play Store is minimal, with a one-time developer account fee of \$25.

Hosting services provided by Firebase further minimized operational expenses.

4.3.3 Revenue Potential:

The app has strong revenue potential through features such as premium subscriptions for experts, ad placements, and in-app purchases.

As the user base grows, additional monetization strategies can be introduced.

Chapter 5

Database

5. Database

Databases form the backbone of any application, serving as the primary storage and retrieval system for user information, application data, and other critical records. For the **Hunermund** app, Firebase Real-time Database was chosen as the database solution, given its robust real-time synchronization capabilities and suitability for mobile app development. This chapter discusses the Firebase Real-time Database in detail and provides a comparison with traditional SQL databases to highlight why Firebase was selected for this project.

5.1 Firebase Real-time Database

Firebase Real-time Database is a cloud-hosted NoSQL database provided by Google. It is specifically designed for applications that require real-time updates and synchronization across multiple clients. Firebase uses a document-based storage structure, where data is organized into JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) trees. This structure allows for flexible and hierarchical data storage, making Firebase ideal for applications with dynamic and interconnected data requirements.

Key Features of Firebase Real-time Database:

5.1.1 Real-Time Synchronization:

Firebase allows multiple devices to access and update the database simultaneously, with changes instantly reflected across all connected clients. This feature ensures that users of the **Hunermund** app always have access to the most up-to-date job postings, profiles, and messages.

5.1.2 Offline Support:

Firebase stores data locally on the user's device when the application is offline. Once the device reconnects to the internet, Firebase automatically synchronizes the offline changes with the cloud database, ensuring data consistency.

5.1.3 Scalability:

Firebase is built to handle large-scale applications with high traffic and data volume, making it suitable for apps like **Hunermund**, which are expected to grow over time.

5.1.4 Security:

Firebase offers built-in authentication and fine-grained access control rules, ensuring that only authorized users can access or modify specific parts of the database.

5.1.5 Ease of Integration:

Firebase provides SDKs (Software Development Kits) for various platforms, including Android, iOS, and web applications, allowing seamless integration with the **Hunermand** app.

Firestore Database Structure in Hunermand

The **Hunermand** app utilizes a hierarchical structure to store data in Firestore, organized into nodes such as users, Experts User, and Jobs. Below is a representation of the database schema:

5.2 Database Structure

Figure 1 : Database Structure

Our data is stored in the Firestore database in the format shown in Figure 1, which represents the structure of our database.

5.2.1 Experts Node:

Figure 2 : Experts User Node

Figure 1 illustrates the structure of the database, including the ExpertsUser node, Jobs node, and Users node. Figure 2 focuses on the ExpertsUser node, which stores all expert user data.

5.2.2 Expert User Details:

Figure 3 : Experts User Details

Figure 3 depicts the data of a single expert user. All expert users have the same type of information, as shown in Figure 3, stored in the database.

5.2.3 Zaroratmand Users Node:

Figure 4 : Zaroramand User Node

Similar to Figure 2, Figure 4 represents all “Zaroratmand” users stored in the database.

5.2.4 Zaroratmand User Details:

Figure 5 : Zaroratmand User Details

Similar to Figure 3, Figure 5 illustrates the data of a single Zaroratmand user. All Zaroratmand users have the same type of information, as shown in Figure 5

5.2.5 Jobs Node:

Figure 6 : Jobs Node

Figure 6 shows the Jobs node, where all job entries are stored.

5.2.6 Post Job Details

Figure 7 : Post Job Details

Figure 7 represents the data for a single job. All jobs contain the same type of information, as shown in Figure 7.

5.3 Example Code Snippet:

Below is an example of how user register and job postings are stored in Firebase:

5.3.1 Zaroratmand User Registration code:

```
val database = FirebaseDatabase.getInstance().getReference(path: "users")
val user = Usersdataclass(cnic, name, email, contactNumber, gender, address, password, confirmPassword)

// Insert into Firebase
database.child(cnic).setValue(user)
    .addOnSuccessListener {
```

Figure 8 : Registration Code of Zaroratmand User

Figure 8 shows the Kotlin code for registering a Zaroratmand user. This code inserts the user's data into the Firebase database and completes the registration process.

5.3.2 Job Posting Code:

```
// Include cnic in the job data
val database = FirebaseDatabase.getInstance().getReference(path: "jobs")
val jobData = PostJobDataclass(
    jobtitle, jobcatagory, jobtype, experience, gender, sallry,
    education, contactPersonName, phonNo, description, location, cnic
)

// Use push() to generate a unique key
val uniqueKey = database.push().key
if (uniqueKey != null) {
    database.child(uniqueKey).setValue(jobData)
        .addOnSuccessListener {
            (activity as? Experts)?.loadFragment(HomeFragment())
            (activity as? Experts)?.getBottomNavigationView()?.selectedItemId = R.id.home
            Toast.makeText(requireContext(), text: "Successfully saved", Toast.LENGTH_LONG).show()
            binding.progressBar.visibility = View.GONE
        }
}
```

Figure 9 : Code of Posting Job

Figure 9 contains the Kotlin code that inserts job data into the Firebase database and completes the job posting process.

5.3.3 ExpertsUser Registration code:

```
private fun saveUserToDatabase(
    cnic: String, name: String, email: String, contactNumber: String, gender: String, address: String, password: String,
    confirmpassword: String, skills: String, experience: String, certificate: String,
    employmentHistory: String, description: String, imageUrl: String
) {
    val database = FirebaseDatabase.getInstance().getReference(path: "ExpertsUser")
    val user = ExpertUserDataclass(cnic, name, email, contactNumber, gender, address, password,
    confirmpassword, skills, experience, certificate, employmentHistory, description, imageUrl)

    database.child(cnic).setValue(user)
        .addOnSuccessListener {
            Toast.makeText(context: this, text: "Data successfully inserted", Toast.LENGTH_LONG).show()
        }
        .addOnFailureListener {
            Toast.makeText(context: this, text: "Failed to insert data", Toast.LENGTH_LONG).show()
        }
}
```

Figure 10 : Registration Code of Expert User

Figure 8 shows the Kotlin code for registering an Expert user. This code inserts the Expert user's data into the Firebase database and completes the registration process.

5.4 Why Firebase Was Chosen

The decision to use Firebase Real-time Database for the **Hunermand** app was based on the following reasons:

5.4.1 Real-Time Synchronization:

Firebase's ability to reflect updates instantly across devices aligns perfectly with the app's need for real-time job listings, profile updates, and messaging.

5.4.2 Ease of Use:

Firebase's simple setup and integration reduced development time and allowed the team to focus on building app features.

5.4.3 Offline Functionality:

Firebase ensures that users can continue using the app without interruption, even when they are offline, which is a critical feature for mobile applications.

5.4.4 Scalability:

As the **Hunermand** app grows, Firebase's horizontal scaling ensures it can handle increasing traffic and data without performance degradation.

Chapter 6

User Interface

6. User Interface

The User Interface (UI) of the Hunermand app was designed with a strong focus on simplicity, functionality and accessibility. The goal was to create an intuitive interface that caters to users with varying levels of technical expertise, ensuring smooth navigation and interaction for both buyers and experts. This chapter details the principles, design decisions, and features of the app's user interface, showing how it enhances the overall user experience.

6.1 Design Principles

The design of the **Hunermand** UI guide the following principles:

6.1.1 Simplicity:

The interface was kept clean and minimalistic, avoiding clutter and unnecessary elements.

Only essential features are display, making it easy for users to understand and use the app.

6.1.2 Accessibility:

The app was designed to be user-friendly for individuals with diverse technical skills.

Large, readable fonts and clear icons were used to enhance usability.

6.1.3 Consistency:

Consistent layouts, colors, and typography were applied across all screens to provide a cohesive experience.

Standard Android design patterns were followed to meet user expectations.

6.1.4 Responsiveness:

The UI was optimized to adapt seamlessly across different screen sizes and device types, ensuring compatibility with a wide range of Android devices.

6.2 Key Screens of the User Interface

Following are the key screens of **Hunermand** application that represent the user interface of **Hunermand** application and their functionalities:

6.2.1 Splash Screen

Figure 11 : Splash Screen

Figure 11 shows the first screen of our **Hunermand** app. When the user opens the app, this screen is displayed to determine the user's status. If the user is logged in as an Expert, they will be redirected to the Jobs screen. If the user is logged in as a Zaroratmand, they will be redirected to the Experts screen. Otherwise, the user will be redirected to the Home screen.

The purpose of this screen to introduce users to the app with branding elements and a professional welcome screen. Displays the app's logo and tagline. A smooth transition leads to the login or home screen after a few seconds.

6.2.2 Login and Registration Screen

Figure 12 : Login and Registration Screen

Figure 12 represents the Home screen of the **Hunermand** app. Non-logged-in or non-registered users will land on this screen when they open the app. From here, users can view Experts, Jobs, and access the Login option.

6.2.3 Enter CNIC Screen

Figure 13 : Enter CNIC Screen

Figure 13 represents the **CNIC** entry screen for the **Hunermand** app registration. On this screen, users will enter their CNIC to either register or sign in to the app.

6.2.4 Enter Password Screen:

Figure 14 : Password Screen

Figure 14 shows the Enter Password screen. After entering their CNIC in Figure 13, if the user is already registered and signed in, they will land on this screen, where they can enter their password.

6.2.5 Registration Form Screen

Figure 15 : Registration Form Screen

Figure 15 represents the Registration Form screen. After entering their CNIC, users will be directed to this screen, where they can enter the personal information required for registration.

6.2.6 Creating Password Screen

The screenshot displays a mobile application interface for creating a password. At the top, there is a blue header bar with a back arrow on the left and system status icons (time 4:10, signal strength, 4G network, and 21% battery) on the right. Below the header is a circular logo for 'HUNERMAND' featuring a house and mountain icon. The main content is a white card with the title 'Create Password'. It contains two text input fields: 'Password' and 'Confirm Password'. Below these fields are two green buttons: 'Register as Hunermand' and 'Register as Zaroratmand'. The bottom of the screen shows a black home indicator bar.

Figure 16 : Creating Password Screen

Figure 16 shows the Create Password screen. After entering their personal details, the user will create a password here. Additionally, the user will choose whether to register as a **Hunermand** or a Zaroratmand. If the user selects Zaroratmand, they will proceed with the Zaroratmand registration. If the user selects Hunermand (expert), they will be redirected to another form to enter their skills details.

6.2.7 Hunermand (Expert) Form

Figure 17 : Expert User Form

Figure 17 represents the Expert Screen. After registering as a Hunermand user, they will enter their skill details here, which are required for the Expert profile.

6.2.8 Home Screen of Expert

Figure 18 : Home Screen For Expert

Figure 18 represents the Home screen of Experts. Here, users can view, find, and search for experts based on their needs.

6.2.9 Experts Screen

Figure 19 : Expert List Screen

Figure 19 shows the Experts screen, where all experts are listed. Users can find and search for experts based on their specific needs.

6.2.10 Post Job Screen

Figure 20 : Post Job Screen

Figure 20 shows the Post Job screen, which is the job posting form. Here, users can insert their job details and post a job based on their requirements.

6.2.11 User Profile

Figure 21 : User Profile Screen

Figure 21 represents the Profile screen of the user. This screen displays the user's posted jobs, where they can delete their posted jobs. By clicking on the three dots, a dropdown menu appears, allowing the user to edit their profile, log out, or delete their account. Additionally, by clicking on the profile image, the user can change their profile picture.

6.2.12 Jobs Screen

Figure 22 : Job List Screen

Figure 22 represents the Jobs screen, where all posted jobs are listed. Users can find and search for jobs based on their skills and requirements.

6.2.13 Home Screen of Jobs

Figure 23 : Home of Jobs

Figure 23 represents the Home screen of Jobs. Here, users can view, find, and search for jobs based on their skill requirements.

6.2.14 Edit Profile Screen

Figure 24 : Edit Profile Screen

Figure 24 represents the **Edit Profile screen**. Here, users can edit their profile information and log out.

Chapter 7

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